

Tara Pacific Consortium Publication Guidelines

Summary of the Tara Pacific Expedition

Coral reefs are the most diverse habitats in the marine realm. Their productivity, structural complexity, and biodiversity critically depend on ecosystem services provided by corals that are threatened because of climate change effects—in particular, ocean warming and acidification. The coral holobiont is composed of the coral animal host, endosymbiotic dinoflagellates, associated viruses, bacteria, and other microeukaryotes. In particular, the mandatory photosymbiosis with microalgae of the family Symbiodiniaceae and its consequences on the evolution, physiology, and stress resilience of the coral holobiont have yet to be fully elucidated. The functioning of the holobiont as a whole is largely unknown, although bacteria and viruses are presumed to play roles in metabolic interactions, immunity, and stress tolerance.

The Tara Pacific project aims to provide a baseline of the “-omics” complexity of the coral holobiont and its ecosystem across the Pacific Ocean and for various oceanographically distinct defined areas. The Tara Pacific expedition (2016–2018) has applied a pan-ecosystemic approach on coral reefs throughout the Pacific Ocean, drawing an east–west transect from Panama to Papua New Guinea and a south–north transect from Australia to Japan, sampling corals throughout 32 island systems with local replicates. Tara Pacific has developed and applied state-of-the-art technologies in very-high-throughput genetic sequencing and molecular analysis to reveal the entire microbial and chemical diversity as well as functional traits associated with coral holobionts, together with various measures on environmental forcing. This ambitious project aims at revealing a massive amount of novel biodiversity, shedding light on the complex links between genomes, transcriptomes, metabolomes, organisms, and ecosystem functions in coral reefs and providing a reference of the biological state of modern coral reefs in the Anthropocene.

Tara Pacific collective names

1. The ***Tara Pacific Consortium*** is composed of institutions, each with a legal representative. The list of institutions and their representatives is given in the Consortium Agreement.
2. The ***Tara Pacific Consortium scientific directors*** are Serge Panes and Denis Allemand.
3. The ***Tara Pacific Consortium Coordinators*** currently include 24 coordinators. The list of Tara Pacific Consortium Coordinators will be updated as the consortium evolves. It is organised in alphabetical order, and includes up-to-date affiliations and ORCID for each coordinator.
4. The ***Tara Pacific Expedition Participants*** include the two scientific directors, the coordinators and anyone involved in designing or implementing the 2016–2018 expedition on land and on board Tara. The list is meant to acknowledge those involved in this first, crucial part of Tara Pacific. It is therefore fixed and will NOT be updated. It is organised in alphabetical order and includes as much as possible ORCIDs, but does NOT include affiliations or email addresses that would need to be updated over time. The list includes a total of 205 participants: 2 scientific directors, 23 coordinators, 124 scientists, 31 crew, 24 guests, and Rainer Friedrich from World Courier. The list is published at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3777760>).

Consortium publications

A piece of work (e.g. a journal article or a data set) is considered to be a **Consortium publication** when it either (1) releases (i.e. first publication of) data from a large fraction (e.g. >50%) of samples collected from any protocol or from a biogeographic region, or (2) results from the collaboration of a large proportion (e.g. >50%) of coordinators as named authors. Decisions are made by the **Tara Pacific Consortium Coordinators** on a case by case basis, following an open vote using online platforms such as Doodle or Google. A decision requires 2/3 majority from at least 3/4 of coordinators. In case a decision is not reached, a discussion with all coordinators is scheduled by the scientific directors within a week and a second vote is organised. In case a decision is not reached on the second vote, the decision is made by the scientific directors. The following guidelines apply to **Consortium publications**. The authors of non-consortium publications are nevertheless encouraged to adopt collaborative and inclusive practices such as those outlined in the present document.

Advance notice of publication

Before starting to work on a publication, e.g. a journal article or a data set, senior authors are required to contact the **Scientific Directors**, so that the **Tara Pacific Consortium Coordinators** can assess if the proposed work constitutes a **Consortium publication**. In case the proposed work constitutes a **Consortium publication**, the **Tara Pacific Consortium Coordinators** are given the opportunity to read a detailed abstract describing the proposed work, and can request to be added individually to either authors list #1 or #3 (see below), and can propose to contribute to the analyses and interpretation of results. In any case, whether a manuscript constitutes a **Consortium publication** or not, the **Tara Pacific Consortium Coordinators** are given the opportunity to read the manuscript, at least 45 days before submission, and have 30 days to request being added individually to authors list #1 or #3 (see below).

Composition and order of named authors on Consortium publications

1. **First author(s)** – We encourage early career scientists to lead consortium papers.
2. **Contributing authors list #1** – should include those whose contribution to either the sampling effort, data generation/analysis, interpretation of results or writing was essential to produce the paper. This list is determined by the first author(s) and the Contributing authors list #3.
3. **Contributing authors list #2** – recognises the contribution of individuals who ensured continuity in the sampling programme. This list is fixed and consists of Clémentine Moulin, Emilie Boissin, Guillaume Bourdin, Guillaume Iwankow, Julie Poulain & Sarah Romac.
4. **Tara Pacific Consortium Coordinators** – The preferred option, if available from the publisher, is to include only the collective author name **Tara Pacific Consortium Coordinators** in the list of authors, and to index all coordinators as authors of the paper, in alphabetical order. This usually involves a note in the list of the authors affiliation, indicating that “the **Tara Pacific Consortium Coordinators** and their affiliations are listed at the end of this manuscript”. The list usually appears before the acknowledgements and coordinators are ordered alphabetically. The list of coordinators and their affiliation is provided at the end of the present document. Coordinators who contributed more specifically to the paper can also be named individually in the contributing authors lists #1 or #3, whichever is more appropriate. The publisher is responsible for deduplicating authors in the different lists so that they are not indexed more than once. In

case the publisher cannot index individuals that are part of a collective author name, all coordinators are named individually as named authors, in alphabetical order.

5. **Tara Pacific Scientific Directors** – Serge Planes & Denis Allemand are named authors.
6. **Contributing authors list #3** – includes senior scientists who contributed particularly to supervising the work, developing its concepts, and/or writing the paper.
7. Anyone can decide not to be part of the named authors.

Acknowledgements

The collective name **Tara Pacific Expedition Participants** is not part of the authors. It appears in the acknowledgements along with a reference to the list of all participants, published at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3777760>). The mandatory acknowledgement text for any publication of the Tara Pacific Consortium is the following:

“Special thanks to the Tara Ocean Foundation, the R/V Tara crew and the Tara Pacific Expedition Participants (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3777760>). We are keen to thank the commitment of the following institutions for their financial and scientific support that made this unique Tara Pacific Expedition possible: CNRS, PSL, CSM, EPHE, Genoscope, CEA, Inserm, Université Côte d’Azur, ANR, agnès b., UNESCO-IOC, the Veolia Foundation, the Prince Albert II de Monaco Foundation, Région Bretagne, Billerudkorsnas, AmerisourceBergen Company, Lorient Agglomération, Oceans by Disney, L’Oréal, Biotherm, France Collectivités, Fonds Français pour l’Environnement Mondial (FFEM), Etienne Bourgois, and the Tara Ocean Foundation teams. Tara Pacific would not exist without the continuous support of the participating institutes. The authors also particularly thank Serge Planes, Denis Allemand, and the Tara Pacific consortium. [\[add further acknowledgement text here\]](#) This is publication number #00 of the Tara Pacific Consortium.”

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